

Polymerization of 1-Octene by $MgCl_2$ -supported $VOCl_3$ Catalyst

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Manuscript received 20 May 1994, revised 24 October 1994, accepted 15 November 1994

$MgCl_2$ -supported $VOCl_3$ catalyst has been prepared and EB used as the internal electron donor. A kinetic study has been made on the polymerization of 1-octene with the above-catalyst activated by $AlEt_3$. The rate of polymerization is directly proportional to the catalyst and monomer concentrations. The activation energy found is 44.84 kJ mol⁻¹. The polymer has been characterised by ¹H and ¹³C nmr, ir and viscosity measurements. The percentage of isotactic polymer produced has been determined. The effect of various external electron donors on the rate of polymerization is studied.

Ziegler-Natta catalysts of greatly improved activity and stereospecificity have been developed using $MgCl_2$ as the support. There are many ways to prepare $MgCl_2$ having high surface area such as ball-milling, precipitation of soluble $MgCl_2$ complex, reaction of magnesium alkoxides with $TiCl_4$ etc. The well known milling method has already been employed in commercial production. However, there still exists a limit to the control of the texture of the catalyst by the simple milling method. Hence much interest has been given to the precipitation methods. Whatever be the type of magnesium compound used, $MgCl_2$ matrix will be ultimately re-formed. In the precipitation method, the solubilisation of $MgCl_2$ in the various media, the recrystallisation of $MgCl_2$ from solution and the effects of electron donors were not yet clearly understood. The above mentioned catalysts are predominantly based on titanium. $MgCl_2$ has been found to be a particularly effective support of $TiCl_4$ for isospecific polymerization of propylene.

The main objective of this work is to investigate the capability of $MgCl_2$ -support in influencing the activity and stereospecificity of the vanadium catalyst and to investigate the kinetics of polymerization of 1-octene (this monomer was preferred because of its low cost and ease of handling with the $VOCl_3$ -supported Ziegler-Natta catalyst).

Results and Discussion

There is good agreement between the chlorine val-

ues found experimentally and those calculated (Table 1). It is obvious from Table 2 that 2-E1H was removed almost completely, whereas a considerable amount of the electron donor remained with the support even after treatment with $VOCl_3$. Both activation of $MgCl_2$ with 2-E1H, EB and $SiCl_4$ to get the support, as well as the treatment of the support with $VOCl_3$ increased the specific surface area several folds from the very small value of anhydrous $MgCl_2$ which can not be measured by BET method (Table 2). A comparison of the X-ray diffraction patterns of the handground anhydrous $MgCl_2$, the support and the catalyst shows that the thermodynamically more stable ccp arrangement in the $MgCl_2$ crystals (Fig. 1a, $2\theta = 15^\circ, 35^\circ$ and 50°) has been changed to hcp arrangement in the support and the catalyst (Figs. 1b, c; the reflections at 35° have

TABLE 1—INORGANIC ELEMENTS IN THE SUPPORT AND THE SUPPORTED CATALYST

Element	Support	Catalyst
Magnesium (wt%)	12.79	13.73
Magnesium (mmol g ⁻¹)	5.26	5.65
Vanadium (wt%)	-	15.55
Vanadium (mmol g ⁻¹)	-	3.05
Chlorine (wt%)	35.66	68.46
Chlorine (found) (mmol g ⁻¹)	10.01	19.30
Chlorine (calcd.) (mmol g ⁻¹)	10.52	20.45

^{*}Chlorine (calculated) = 2 [Mg] and 2 [Mg] + 3 [V] for the support and the catalyst respectively.

TABLE 2—AMOUNT OF ORGANIC COMPONENTS IN THE SUPPORT AND SUPPORTED CATALYST AND SURFACE AREA

Support or catalyst	Alcohol wt%	Ethyl benzoate wt%	BET surface area $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$
$\text{MgCl}_2/2\text{EtH}/\text{EB}$ (Support)	15.4	28.91	3.6
$\text{MgCl}_2/2\text{EtH}/\text{EB}/\text{VOCl}_3$ (Catalyst)	0	12.2	26.7

Fig. 1. X-Ray diffraction patterns of (a) handground anhydrous MgCl_2 , (b) $\text{MgCl}_2/2\text{EtH}/\text{EB}$ support and (c) $\text{MgCl}_2/2\text{EtH}/\text{EB}/\text{VOCl}_3$ catalyst.

diminished or vanished; peaks at 15° and 50° have broadened) with rotational disorder of MgCl_2 crystals^{1,2} (new peaks at $21\text{--}25^\circ$ in the support and $21\text{--}25^\circ$ and $29\text{--}30^\circ$ in the catalyst).

The productivity of the supported VOCl_3 catalyst was found to be slightly more than that of the un-

ported catalyst³ (1.62 and 1.53 g polyoctene/g V) may be due to the very small increase in the number of active centers on supporting VOCl_3 on MgCl_2 , whereas productivity of TiCl_4 catalysts increased to several folds when supported on MgCl_2 ^{4,5} (1.75 to 10.38 g polyoctene/g V). Also, the MgCl_2 -supported TiCl_4 catalyst⁴ was found to be more active towards 1-octene polymerization compared to the MgCl_2 -supported VOCl_3 catalysts, which may be due to the higher concentration of the active centers in the former catalyst as reported⁶ for propylene polymerization.

Kinetics : The kinetics of polymerization of 1-octene were studied with the catalyst system $\text{MgCl}_2/2\text{EtH}/\text{EB}/\text{VOCl}_3\text{-AlEt}_3$. In the present study, the principal factors which seemed to affect the kinetics are discussed below.

During the polymerization of 1-octene by the present catalyst system, the rate reached a maximum value within 1h and then it decreased. This may be due to the completion of active center formation within 1h and the decrease in rate after that may be attributed to the deactivation of active centers. The molecular weight of the polymers increased with increasing reaction time.

Ageing the catalyst components resulted in a decrease of conversion, which may be due to the fast deactivation of active centers formed before adding the monomer, as well as molecular weight of the polymer. Hence in the present study, the catalyst components were not aged prior to polymerization.

Fig. 2(a, b) show the first order dependence of the rate of polymerization on the monomer and the catalyst concentrations respectively. The molecular weight of the polymer increased with increasing monomer concentration and decreased with increasing catalyst concentrations indicating chain transfer to the catalyst and absence of chain transfer to the monomer (Fig. 3).

Under conditions where a supported catalyst is used, a considerable amount of the alkyl added will be tied up in reactions with the internal donor which is present in the catalyst. Hence deviations should be expected to occur at low concentrations of the alkyl. So the

Fig. 2. Effect of (a) monomer concentration, (b) catalyst concentration on the rate of polymerization of 1-octene and (c) the Langmuir-Hinshelwood plot.

polymerization reactions were carried out at considerably higher alkyl aluminium concentrations. Maximum conversion was observed at an Al/V ratio of 133. At higher ratios the molecular weight decreased with in-

Fig. 3. Effect of (a) monomer concentration, (b) catalyst concentration, (c) co-catalyst concentration and (d) temperature on the molecular weight of the polymers.

creasing Al/V ratio indicating the involvement of the aluminium alkyl in chain breaking processes. The dependence of the rate of polymerization on the aluminium alkyl concentration is explained on the basis of the Langmuir-Hinshelwood mechanism.

The activation energy of the overall polymerization (was found to be $44.84 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ from the Arrhenius plot) is in agreement with those reported by other authors^{7,8} for the polymerization by the coordinated two-step mechanism. The molecular weight of the polymers decreased with increasing temperature (Fig. 3).

Effect of a few external electron donors was studied. Among the four donors used, methyl-*p*-toluate and EB were found to be the efficient ones with respect to both rate and molecular weight (Table 3). Hence, a two-step coordinate anionic mechanism based on the Langmuir-Hinshelwood model (involving competitive adsorption of both monomer and aluminium alkyl on the catalyst surface) is proposed. The rate of polymerization (under conditions where $[M]$ is constant), is given by

$$R_p = \frac{k_p c^* K_A [A]}{(1 + K_A [A])^2}$$

where c^* is the concentration of the active centers, K_A the equilibrium constant for the adsorption of the alkyl on the catalyst surface and k_p the rate constant for

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF EXTERNAL ELECTRON DONORS ON THE RATE OF POLYMERIZATION AND MOLECULAR WEIGHT OF POLYMER

Name of the electron donor	$10^5 R_p$ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹	Mol. wt. 10^4
Methyl- <i>p</i> -toluate ^a	0.97	12.35
2,6-Di- <i>t</i> -butyl-paracresol ^b	0.61	10.56
Ethyl benzoate ^a	0.99	12.02
Phenyltriethoxy-silane ^c	0.60	11.13

^aAl/electron donor = 3, ^bAl/electron donor = 20, ^cAl/electron donor = 5.

propagation. Thus, a plot of $([A]/R_p)^{1/2}$ vs $[A]$ should be linear. Fig. 2c shows that such plot is almost a straight line.

Polymer characterisation : The ir spectrum of poly-1-octene showed bands at 2 920 (strong and intense), 2 850 (strong), 1 460, 1 370 and 720 cm^{-1} (small) due to the methyl C-H stretching, methylene C-H stretching, methyl C-H bending, methylene C-H bending and methylene deformation respectively. The ^1H nmr spectrum of poly-1-octene prepared using the catalyst system under study showed singlets at δ 1.75 and 1.25 due to the backbone methine and the methylene groups and triplet at δ 0.85 due to the methyl group. The low-field C^3 (the first side-chain methylene carbon) signal appearing at 35.06 ppm, in the ^1H -decoupled ^{13}C nmr spectrum of poly-1-octene was used^{9,10} for calculating the isotactic content by the cutting-weighing method. It was found that the present catalyst system produced 46% isotactic polymer which is higher than that produced by unsupported VOCl_3 catalyst³ (27%) but lower than that produced by the MgCl_2 -supported TiCl_4 catalyst⁴.

The productivity and the stereospecificity of the VOCl_3 catalyst towards 1-octene polymerization was increased by supporting VOCl_3 on MgCl_2 . From the first order dependence of the rate of polymerization on the monomer and catalyst concentrations, the activation energy and the straight line plot of $([A]/R_p)^{1/2}$ vs $[A]$, a coordinate anionic mechanism based on Langmuir-Hinshelwood model is proposed for 1-octene polymerization.

Experimental

EB , VOCl_3 , anhydrous MgCl_2 and AlEt_3 were prepared according to reported procedures¹¹⁻¹³. All the solvents were purified according to standard procedures. 1-Octene (Sigma) was purified by refluxing over sodium for 5 h, then distilled and stored over calcium hydride. Nitrogen was purified by passing through Fieser's solution, H_2SO_4 , CaCl_2 and finally a tube containing molecular sieves (3Å). The method of preparation of MgCl_2 -supported VOCl_3 catalyst and the polymerization procedure are similar to that of MgCl_2 -

supported TiCl_4 catalysts⁴.

Mg , Cl , V and the organic components in the support and the supported catalyst were estimated by EDTA, Mohr's titrations, spectrophotometric methods (Shimadzu 160 A) and hydrolysis GC⁴ respectively. The surface area of the support and the catalyst were measured by nitrogen adsorption technique at -195° in a Carlo-Erba-Strumentazione Sorptomat 1800 instrument. The samples were degassed at 25° . The structural changes occurring in the MgCl_2 crystals upon activation were studied by X-ray diffraction technique using a Rigaku Miniflex instrument operating at 40 kV using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation in the range $5^\circ < 2\theta < 60^\circ$. The sample was covered with a thin polyethylene terephthalate film and loaded into the diffractometer.

The polymers were characterised by ir, ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectroscopy and viscosity measurements. Ir spectra (CHCl_3) were measured on a Perkin-Elmer 781 spectrophotometer, ^1H nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian EM 390 spectrometer (90 MHz) at 27° and ^1H -decoupled ^{13}C nmr spectra on a Jeol JNM instrument (400 MHz) at 27° operating at 100.4 MHz, in CDCl_3 and TMS as the internal standard. The molecular weight was determined using viscosity measurements⁴.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (M.S.) wishes to thank C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the financial assistance.

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